

does not begin until June or July. Because the crop grows in dry soil for 2 to 4 months, it does not benefit from the increase in pH on flooding, which lowers the harmful levels of aluminum.

Plants of the traditional variety Nang Kiew with orange-yellow discolorations were sampled on 23 June near Bang-or. The crop had been broadcast on 10 May

on soil classified as Sulfic Tropaquept. The affected plants had higher aluminum and lower phosphorus contents than healthy plants from the same field.

Aluminum toxicity in wetland rice has received relatively little attention because the high amount of dissolved aluminum normally disappears soon after flooding, even on very acid soils. Aluminum

toxicity may be a major factor limiting production in deep-water rice an acid sulfate soils as long as good irrigation facilities are lacking and no fertilizer is applied. Introduction of varieties adapted to high aluminum and low phosphorus should help increase rice production in the area. **W**

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

International rice testing program

Three IRTP monitoring tours in 1977

In 1977, the International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) sponsored three monitoring tours to enable rice scientists from various countries to observe the performance of materials from different sources in the international nurseries and to become better acquainted with other rice research in the regions.

The first tour focused on rice in the arid regions. All participants visited Sudan, Egypt, and Pakistan, and several visited Punjab state, India. The group observed the vast potential for rice production in the region and similar breeding objectives in various countries in the region. They noted that many current IRTP entries from the humid tropics were not suited to the region and that active local breeding programs were developing promising materials. The group therefore recommended the establishment of an International Rice Arid Regions Observational Nursery (IRARON) where national programs in the region could enter their best rices along with selected entries from IRRI and other IRTP nurseries. Entries should have the following traits: high yielding ability; long, slender grain (scented and nonscented); early maturity (110 – 130 days); tolerance to salinity, alkalinity, and zinc deficiency; early growth vigor; resistance to stem borer, blast, and brown spot; and tolerance to high temperature. Dr. M. S. Balal of Egypt will pack and dispatch the nurseries to interested arid-region scientists in March 1978. The IRTP will make field books and analyze and publish the results. Those

Scientists on the IRTP monitoring tour to East India and Nepal inspecting an International Upland Rice Observational Nursery at the Rice Research Station, Ranchi, Bihar, India.

interested in conducting the nursery should contact the Joint Coordinator of IRTP at IRRI.

The second IRTP monitoring tour focused on rice improvement in Nepal and northern India. In Nepal's Kathmandu Valley, varieties need some cold tolerance and blast resistance. The Tarai area of Nepal is similar to Bihar state, India, where bacterial blight is a major constraint. Drought was the major problem in southern Bihar and in the Faizabad area of eastern Uttar Pradesh, India. Gall midge was a major constraint around Cuttack and Bhubaneswar, India. The group recommended earlier dispatch of the IRTP nurseries to enable timely planting at all locations. They also

recommended entries for the 1978 nurseries and discussed some improvements in the methodology and conduct of future IRTP nurseries.

The third tour was after an IRTP planning conference for Latin America, held at the International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) in Colombia. It focused on upland rice in Central America and Mexico. The group noted the favorable rainfall patterns and soil types in the region. Yields of many varieties often reached 5 to 6 t/ha. Blast, sheath blight, and leaf scald damaged some varieties considerably at certain locations. The group recommended that efforts to develop varieties with stable blast resistance for the region be

intensified and that regional rice improvement programs expand the genetic diversity of their breeding materials. The need for more training of rice scientists and for additional support to national rice research programs was evident to the group.

Below is a list of participants in IRTP monitoring tours during 1977.

1. *Arid regions tour* (Sudan, Egypt, and Pakistan)
 - G. Ghobrial, Sudan
 - M. S. Bald, Egypt

- M. Moafizad, Iran
- A. M. Farkhonde, Iran
- G. McLean, Ford Foundation, Egypt
- M. Rosero, CIAT/IRRI, Colombia
- W. R. Coffman, IRRI
- H. E. Kauffman, IRRI

2. *Nepal and northern India tour*

- A. N. M. R. Karim, Bangladesh
- M. Nasiruddin, Bangladesh
- H. K. Pande, India
- D. N. Borthakur, India
- G. Verma, India
- S. Saran, India

- B. B. Shahi, Nepal
- K. P. Shreshta, Nepal
- D. V. Seshu, IRRI
- J. C. O'Toole, IRRI

3. *Central America and Mexico tour*

- J. I. Murillo, Costa Rica
- W. R. Pazos, Guatemala
- L. H. Aragon, Mexico
- E. Espinosa, Panama
- M. Rosero, CIAT/IRRI, Colombia
- S. K. De Datta, IRRI
- D. V. Seshu, IRRI
- H. E. Kauffman, IRRI

Pest management and control

DISEASES

Potash nutrition and sheath blight disease

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The effect of potash application on the development of sheath blight, caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*, was investigated in a pot-culture experiment during the 1976 wet season (June–September) with ADT 31 used as the susceptible rice variety. Muriate of potash as basal

dressing was applied at 0,49,99, 148, 198, and 247 kg K₂O/ha (converted from kg/acre). Nitrogen at 123 kg/ha was applied as urea and phosphorus at 62 kg P₂O₅/ha as superphosphate to all treatments. Disease intensity and yield were recorded.

Potassium application reduced the disease incidence significantly. As the potash levels increased, the disease incidence decreased, with a corresponding increase in yield (see table). Investigation reveals that potash nutrition gives rice resistance to sheath blight.

Sapporo, where natural occurrence of ragged stunt had not been observed.

Of 40 insects that received the supernate injection, 21 survived for 2 weeks afterward. They were used to inoculate seedlings of the rice variety Mihonishiki, at 3 insects/seedling for an inoculation feeding period of 3 days. The same insects were then transferred to inoculate another set of seedlings for 3 days. All 14 inoculated seedlings developed symptoms of the disease.

In addition to supporting the viral nature of ragged stunt, the experiment showed that the injection method can be used in bioassay of the virus.

Effect of potash on the incidence of sheath blight disease. Tamil Nadu, India.

Potash level (kg K ₂ O/ha)	Mean disease index	Decrease in disease over control (%)	Mean grain yield (g/pot)	Increase in yield over control (%)
0	81	–	11	–
49	76	6	11	6
99	65	20	12	15
148	61	24	14	26
198	55	33	15	42
247	49	39	16	50

C.D. (P = 0.01)

Bioassay of rice ragged stunt virus

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The infectivity of rice ragged stunt virus was determined by the injection method

at the University of Hokkaido, Japan. Fresh leaves of diseased plants of IR3839-1, infected in the Philippines, were macerated in a buffer solution and centrifuged. The supernate was injected by a fine glass capillary into the body of brown planthoppers *Nilaparvata lugens*. The insects had been reared for years in

Ragged stunt disease in Thailand

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Ragged stunt disease, transmitted by *Nilaparvata lugens*, was first noted in Thailand by Dr. E. A. Heinrichs, IRRI entomologist, during an October 1977 visit to the Bangkhen and Rangsit Rice Experiment Stations. It caused serious yield losses in the variety RD7 around Bangkok at the end of the 1977 wet season. About 3,200 ha of RD7 in Chachengsao province, central plains region, were severely infected; in many